

Core Career Paths: How do we make changes that are enduring and embedded in workplace culture, policy and systems?

11.00am to 12.30pm (90mins), Monday 28th October 2024

Presenters and co-facilitators

- Adjunct Professor Sach Jayasinghe
- Emeritus Professor Joe Shapter
- Professor Ute Roessner

Panel

- Dr Nyssa Drinkwater
- Associate Professor Josh Lipton-Duffin
- Dr Maria Soliman
- Paul Collins

Session Outline – Why it matters

A typical research infrastructure specialist (e.g., microscopist, bioinformatician, software developer, process engineer, etc) not only has to have direct experience in applying deep technical know-how to research projects, but must also possess professional attributes of customer service, business development and general commercial acumen, thus blurring the lines of the ‘professional’ and ‘academic’ roles as stipulated in enterprise agreements of most Australian research institutions. They may either be degree-qualified with direct technical experience or PhD graduates who have chosen an alternative path away from independent research. Despite this particular workforce existing for more than a decade, the sector has not resolved the issue of how best to support the career progression of such ‘blended professionals’, which impacts our ability to recruit and retain the best. The 2021 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap noted: “...one of the immediate priorities for the Expert NRI Advisory Group will be: development of a NRI Workforce Strategy to support career pathways, address technical skills shortages and identify capability gaps. NRI is underpinned by a highly skilled and increasingly specialised workforce that needs job security and opportunities for career mobility and professional development.” The session will explore the complex challenge, dissecting institutional, national and global context and consider what is required to make enduring change in support of core career paths.

The Challenge – National Perspective

“...one of the immediate priorities for the Expert NRI Advisory Group will be: development of a NRI Workforce Strategy to support career pathways, address technical skills shortages and identify capability gaps. NRI is underpinned by a highly skilled and increasingly specialised workforce that needs job security and opportunities for career mobility and professional development.” 2021 Roadmap

The Challenge – Institutional Perspective

- Higher education dichotomy of Academic (about individual) vs Professional (about job) – cultural bias, two class system
- Is there such a concept as a professional scientist?
- PhD vs non-PhD....accommodating senior Engineers
- Reward and recognition during promotions – no fit-for-purpose KPIs, no benchmarks
- Questions of equity and equality for those that contribute to R&D and innovation ecosystem, including clear career paths
 - Equal opportunity – it's not about every individual pursuing career advancement
 - Equity – there needs to be a path for all to advance, but an individual has choice
 - Recognition in outputs, grants, etc (not just for promotion)

What is the CORE issue?

Ranking Poll 127 participants

Responding to the Challenge – Institutional

- Exemplars

- ANU

- Rolling out a new professional stream framework – Technical Specialist – with more appropriate classification criteria for research infrastructure staff
 - If academic, have utilised Academic in Practice stream for academic RI staff
 - Will explore evolving academic stream more appropriate for RI staff, similarly to UoM and UQ

- QUT

- Established the Research Infrastructure Specialist job family within Academic Track
 - Enshrined changes within the Academic Career Framework
 - PVCRI role ensures ongoing advocacy and is part of RI staff academic promotion decisions

Responding to the Challenge – National

- NRI Workforce Strategy
- UK-based Technician Commitment
 - The Commitment aims to ensure visibility, recognition, career development and sustainability for technicians working in higher education and research, across all disciplines. Universities and research institutes are invited to become signatories of the Technician Commitment and pledge action to tackle the key challenges affecting their technical staff. Scroll down to learn more.

Responding to the Challenge – Voice for RI Workforce

- Institutional support mixed within Australian universities and research organisations;
- No obvious advocacy leadership in Australia; and
- Support for a dedicated entity indicated via survey of RI community, including support for structured RI staff training and development (non-technical skills)

Time to give voice to the talent behind research infrastructure

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Central Analytical Research Facility, QUT

Sach Jayasinghe

Consultant ♦ Higher Education ♦ R&D ♦ Research Infrastructure

1 article

There has been ongoing discourse on the idea of a ‘third stream’ within the Australian higher education workforce profile. Recently, Bare *et al* (2021) notes that the “Pandemic provides an opportunity to reset and rethink”, and there are solutions to “entrenched current and emerging higher education workforce problems”. The need for a third stream correlates with the rise of the ‘blended professional’: staff roles that span the characteristics of professional and academic domains (Whitchurch, 2009). When applied to research infrastructure, the concept of the ‘blended professional’ has direct relevance. A typical research infrastructure specialist (e.g., microscopist, bioinformatician, software developer, process engineer, etc) not only has to have direct experience in applying deep technical know-how to research projects, but must also possess professional attributes of customer service, business

Academy for Collaborative Research Infrastructure

is an independent, not-for-profit, organisation established to serve the research infrastructure community

[Find out more](#)

- NFP limited by guarantee (ACN:672 898 645)
- Members-based entity - membership by individuals (RI staff) enshrined in Constitution
- Members can be sponsored by institutions
- ACRI Objectives:
 - Advocacy – drive change
 - Professional development and education
 - Knowledge dissemination

You can become a member via the ACRI website www.acri.org.au

Profile of the Workforce

- A. I oversee select research infrastructure (equipment and spaces), focussed on local end-user induction, equipment maintenance and upkeep (often described as technical services). I do not normally contribute to experimental design or develop new methods.
- B. I am an academic (e.g., research fellow, post-doc) who has part-time responsibility in leading and managing select research infrastructure capabilities. The said capability is intimately linked with my independent research discipline.
- C. I am a specialist technologist, scientist, engineer, software developer or informatician that enables leveraging of research infrastructure. My intellectual contributions are often acknowledged through authorship or other research outputs. I do not conduct independent research but focus on novel method development and advancing technology.

RI workforce profile - which statement best describes you?

Multiple Choice Poll 112 votes 112 participants

A - 61 votes

B - 9 votes

C - 42 votes

Panel Session

- Dr Nyssa Drinkwater
- Associate Professor Josh Lipton-Duffin
- Dr Maria Soliman
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Audience Q&A

- “Recognition suggestion - University announcements of major wins where key professional/research specialist staff who were involved are named as well as the PI
- For major infrastructure grants, having expert technical staff salary FTEs embedded within the grant would be a good first step
- Re recognition. It would be great to be included at the project planning stage. We have the expertise to know whether a test is feasible
- Recognition is also challenging when you have multiple facilities within the same institute working in similar fields and one gets favoured over the other
- Recognition by engagement in the research is a deep cultural challenge. Some organisations totally preclude that occurring, and others embrace it.”

Take Home Notes

- Enduring change requires both top-down (e.g. Technicians Commitment) and bottom-up approaches (e.g. ACRI)
- Whilst the University EBAs are an impediment, culture and lack of sector-wide advocacy for change are the main issues
- The local level institutional responses (e.g. QUT, ANU, UniMelb) have demonstrated that the EBAs can be flexible
- The sector-wide change is key to talent mobility and retention
- The career path options need to recognise the nuances of the RI workforce. There are those that demonstrate academic-like metrics and outputs and those that are ‘masters of their tools’, but may not necessarily produce traditional research outputs

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